

Clivia robusta

Swamp Clivia

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Group: Monocot

Size: 1.6 – 1.8 m

Distribution:

Clivia robusta is endemic to South Africa, confined to the Pondoland Centre in the Eastern Cape and southern KwaZulu-Natal. It occurs in a narrow coastal belt (100–500 m altitude) from Port St. Johns to the Mzimkulu River, in damp, shaded habitats such as forest margins, streambanks, and swamps.

Importance:

Clivia robusta is adapted to wetlands, where it helps stabilise streambanks and saturated soils. It is also used in interspecific breeding to produce vigorous hybrids.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 644.36 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 15.81 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 17.69 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.3% [Single: 70.8%, Duplicated: 28.5%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 37 074.83 kilobases

Contig number: 2 741

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